

Second Dissociation Constant of Oxalic Acid from 0° to 50°

A. K. SINHA, J. C. GHOSH and B. PRASAD

Department of Chemistry, Patna University, Patna

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The second dissociation constant and the corresponding ΔH and ΔC_p of oxalic acid from 0° to 50° at 5° interval have been determined by Harned and Fallon and also by Pinching and Bates. The values of $\log K_2$ obtained by them differ by 2 to 5 in the second place of decimal.

Recalculated values of $\log K_2$ using the experimental data of both sets of the workers and the method developed in this laboratory, generally differ from each other within 2 in the third place. On the basis of recalculation, $\log K_2$ is given by the equation,

$$-\log K_2 = \frac{950.77}{T} - 2.57503 + 0.98055 \times 10^{-2} \cdot T + 0.83179 \times 10^{-5} \cdot T^2$$

over the range of temperature 0° to 50°.

FROM cell (C-1)
 $H_2 | NaHOx(m_1), Na_2Ox(m_2), NaCl(m_3), AgCl | Ag$
 ... (C-1)

Harned and Fallon¹ and from cell (C-2)

$H_2 | KHOx(m_1), Na_2Ox(m_2), NaCl(m_3), AgCl | Ag$
 ... (C-2)

Pinching and Bates² found the second dissociation constant, K_2 of oxalic acid from 0° to 50° at 5° interval. While Harned and Fallon worked from $\mu = 0.03$ to 0.17, Pinching and Bates worked from $\mu = 0.07$ to 0.70. Harned and Fallon used the following two equations (1) and (2)

$$\frac{(E-E^0)F}{2.3026RT} + \log \frac{m_{Cl} \cdot m_{HOX}}{m_{OX}} + \frac{2A\sqrt{\mu}}{1+b\sqrt{2\mu}} = -\log K_2 + f(\mu) \quad \dots (1)$$

$$\frac{(E-E^0)F}{2.3026RT} + \log \frac{m_{Cl} \cdot m_{HOX}}{m_{OX}} + 2A\sqrt{\mu} = -\log K_2 + f'(\mu) \quad \dots (2)$$

Pinching and Bates used equation (3) given below :

$$\frac{(E-E^0)F}{2.3026RT} + \log m_{Cl} + \log \frac{m_{HOX}}{m_{OX}} + \frac{2A\sqrt{\mu}}{1+B\bar{a}\sqrt{\mu}} = -\log K_2 - \beta^* \mu \quad \dots (3)$$

b used in equation (1) was taken to be unity. β^* and \bar{a} used in equation (3) are adjustable parameters. Harned and Fallon used both equations (1) and (2) without correcting the ratio m_{HOX}/m_{OX} and also after correcting the ratio for m_H by taking an approximate value of K_2 . In equation (3) Pinching and Bates

also used approximate value of m_H for correcting the ratio m_{HOX}/m_{OX} . The values of $\log K_2$ thus found by the two sets of workers differ from each other by not less than 0.02 and sometimes by nearly 0.03 at all the temperatures considered.

The experimental work of these two sets of workers were thorough. We therefore decided to recalculate the values of K_2 by our method (without assigning any approximate value of K_2) using the experimental data of these two sets of workers.

Results and Discussion

Assuming $\gamma_H \cdot \gamma_{Cl}$ to be independent of the composition of the ionic atmosphere in very dilute solution³, β in the equation (4) given below will be the same, whether we use (i) pure HCl, (ii) a mixture of NaHOx, Na_2Ox , NaCl (Harned and Fallon's cell) or (iii) a mixture of KHOx, Na_2Ox , NaCl (Pinching and Bates' cell).

$$-\log \gamma_H \cdot \gamma_{Cl} = \frac{2A\sqrt{\mu}}{1+\sqrt{\mu}} - \beta\mu \quad \dots (4)$$

The e.m.f. given by cells (C-1) and (C-2) as also cell (C-3) given below will be given by equation (5).

$$E + \frac{2.3026RT}{F} \log m_H \cdot m_{Cl} - \frac{2.3026RT}{F} \frac{2A\sqrt{\mu}}{1+\sqrt{\mu}} = E^0 - \frac{2.3026RT}{F} \beta\mu \quad \dots (5)$$

$H_2 | HCl(m), AgCl | Ag$... (C-3)

Cell (C-3) was used by Harned and Ehlers⁴ and utilising their data and equation (5) given above, the

values of β at different temperatures were calculated and are recorded in Table I. It may be mentioned that wherever international volt was used we converted it to absolute volt.

In cell (C-1) or (C-2) an arbitrary value is assigned to μ and β is taken from Table I, and m_H corresponding to this μ is calculated from equation (5).

$$\text{Now, } \mu = m_1 + 3m_2 + m_3 + 2m_H \quad \dots (6)$$

TABLE I. VALUES OF β FROM 0° TO 50°.

Temp. °C	β	Temp. °C	β
0	0.464	30	0.476
5	0.456	35	0.465
10	0.444	40	0.467
15	0.460	45	0.469
20	0.480	50	0.459
25	0.490	—	—

Hence a new value of μ is calculated. This is fed in equation (5). The process is repeated till m_H is constant upto eighth place of decimal. This is taken as the correct value of m_H .

$$\text{Now, } m_{OX} = m_2 + m_H$$

$$\text{and } m_{HOX} = m_1 - m_H$$

Fig. 1.

Fig. 2.

Hence m_H , m_{HOX} , m_{OX} and μ are known.

$$\text{Now, } K_2 = \frac{m_H \cdot m_{OX}}{m_{HOX}} \cdot \frac{\gamma_H \cdot \gamma_{OX}}{\gamma_{HOX}}$$

$$\text{or, } \log K_2 = \log \frac{m_H \cdot m_{OX}}{m_{HOX}} - \frac{4A\sqrt{\mu}}{1+\sqrt{\mu}} + B\mu.$$

$$\text{Putting } \log \frac{m_H \cdot m_{OX}}{m_{HOX}} - \frac{4A\sqrt{\mu}}{1+\sqrt{\mu}} = q$$

$$\text{We get, } q = \log K_2 - B\mu \quad \dots (7)$$

Confining roughly to $\mu = 0.2$, Fig. 1 shows some typical plots of q against μ , from the data of Harned and Fallon and Fig. 2 shows the same from the data of Pinching and Bates. At $\mu = 0$, $q = \log K_2$. The values of $\log K_2$ recalculated from the data of both sets of authors agree within 0.002, except at 5° when the difference is 0.004, but the recalculated values differ appreciably from the values of the two sets of workers as shown in table 2.

Recalculated values of $-\log K_2$ are given by the equation

$$-\log K_2 = \frac{950.77}{T} - 2.57503 + 0.98055 \times 10^{-2} \cdot T + 0.83179 \times 10^{-5} \cdot T^2 \quad \dots (8)$$

TABLE 2. THE DISSOCIATION CONSTANT K_2 OF REACTION $HOX^- \rightleftharpoons H^+ + OX^{2-}$

Temp. in °C	-log K_2			
	Harned Fallon	Ours from H & F	Pinching Bates	Ours from P & B
0	4.228	4.212	4.201	4.210
5	4.235	4.220	4.207	4.216
10	4.244	4.227	4.218	4.227
15	4.255	4.240	4.231	4.240
20	4.268	4.256	4.247	4.254
25	4.286	4.273	4.266	4.272
30	4.308	4.296	4.287	4.295
35	4.331	4.320	4.312	4.318
40	4.356	4.348	4.338	4.349
45	4.388	4.379	4.369	4.379
50	4.417	4.409	4.399	4.409

Our assumption requires that the value of B in equation (7) obtained from plots shown in Fig. 1 and Fig. 2 should be the same. This was actually found to be true.

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TABLE 3

ΔH AND ΔC_p OF THE REACTION $HOX^- = H^+ + OX^{2-}$

Temp. in °C.	- ΔH in cal.			- ΔC_p in cal/degree		
	Harned & Fallon	Pinching & Bates	Ours from eqn. (9)	Harned & Fallon	Pinching & Bates	Ours from eqn. (10)
0	278	346	550	43	50	42
5	501	600	761	46	51	43
10	739	857	977	49	52	44
15	993	1120	1198	52	53	45
20	1264	1387	1425	56	54	46
25	1551	1659	1658	59	55	47
30	1856	1936	1896	63	56	48
35	2178	2217	2139	66	57	49
40	2519	2502	2389	70	58	51
45	2877	2793	2644	74	58	52
50	3256	3088	2906	77	59	53

obtained from standard statistical methods. Hence ΔH and ΔC_p are given by

$$\Delta H = 4349.7 - 4.48602 \times 10^{-2} \cdot T^2 - 7.61088 \times 10^{-5} \cdot T^3 \quad \dots (9)$$

$$\Delta C_p = -8.97204 \times 10^{-2} \cdot T - 22.8326 \times 10^{-5} \cdot T^2 \quad (10)$$

The values of ΔH and ΔC_p obtained by us and those by Harned and Fallon and Pinching and Bates are given in Table 3.

References

1. H. S. HARNED and L. D. FALLON, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 61, 3111.
2. G. D. PINCHING and R. G. BATES, *J. Nat. Bur. Stand.*, 1943, 40, 405.
3. G. SAHU and B. PRASAD, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1969, 46, 933.
4. (i) H. S. HARNED and R. W. EHLERS, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 54, 1350.
(ii) H. S. HARNED and R. W. EHLERS, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 55, 2179.